

MECHANICAL AND FIRE CHARACTERISTICS OF POLYPROPYLENE COMPOSITES USING AMMONIUM POLYPHOSPHATE AND CHICKEN FEATHER FIBRES

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Manufacturing

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Rise in research for sustainable flame retardant solutions

Which Material Needs Repurposing?

Source: IHS Consulting 2020

Improves specific strength of composites

Improves flame retardancy

Good Acoustic and insulating properties

Biodegradable

Low density of composites (**0.8 g/cc**)

Ratio of Tensile strength to density for animal fibres

Source: satista.com

- NFRC are thermally unstable.
- Upon heating, natural fibres release volatile gaseous products.
- IFR based on Ammonium polyphosphate (APP) results in phosphorous-nitrogen synergism during combustion, IFR forms intumescent char

Impact of Ammonium Polyphosphate on PP Composites

- Addition of Ammonium Polyphosphate helps in improving the flame retardancy of PP composites
- Addition of Ammonium Polyphosphate is a deterrent for PP composite's mechanical properties.

- With the composite comprising 50% polymer and 50% of treated feather fibre that is repurposed waste.
- Overall there is an improvement in sustainable composites manufacturing with improved flame retardancy and mechanical properties.

Manufacturing:

Melamine Phosphate Treatment for Keratinous Fibres

Granulating dried
chicken feathers
into fibres

Phosphoric Acid
solution

1

2

Melamine

Powder Mixer

Powder Mixer

Melamine Phosphate treated
keratinous fibres

To achieve flame retardancy with a minimum amount of APP

Material Characterisations

UL-94 / Vertical Burn Tests

FRCFF/PP/0APP

FRCFF/PP/2APP

FRCFF/PP/4APP

FRCFF/PP/6APP

NR

NR

V1

V0

Cone Calorimeter Results

HRR of neat Polypropylene, 30% Chicken feather-polypropylene composite, 50% Flame retardant chicken feather-polypropylene composite, 20% Ammonium polyphosphate-polypropylene composite

HRR of 50% Flame retardant chicken feather-polypropylene composite, 48% Flame retardant chicken feather-polypropylene-2%APP composite, 46% Flame retardant chicken feather-polypropylene-4%APP composite, 44% Flame retardant chicken feather-polypropylene-6%APP composite, 20% Ammonium polyphosphate-polypropylene composite

Cone Calorimeter Results

Neat PP

PP/20APP
composite

- The composite containing 48 wt.% FRCFF and 2 wt.% APP achieves a remarkable reduction of PHRR (peak heat release rate) (~73%) compared to one of neat PP
- Furthermore, the UL-94/vertical burn tests showed that the composite based on 44 wt.% FRCFF and 6 wt.% APP accomplished a V-0 rating, indicating self-extinguishment without any drippings.

- An improvement in the tensile strength of composites is observed with the sequential addition of APP.
- The drop in tensile strength was effectively arrested with the low loading of APP in the presence of FRCFF.
- These data are against traditional knowledge on APP's detrimental effects on polymers' mechanical strength.

Numerical Simulation of Cone Calorimeter Performance

Cone calorimeter setup: (a) Experimental, (b) FDS simulation. A computational domain of $400 \times 400 \times 500$ mm with a cell size of 6.7 mm was defined, and a heat flux of 50 kW/m^2 was established by setting the cone heater temperature to 750°C .

Numerical Simulation of Cone Calorimeter Performance

In the simulation, the composite sample was modelled as a homogeneous single layer consisting of several materials, namely flax, PP and APP with appropriate thermal and physical properties.

Since Fire Dynamics Simulation is limited to simulating thermophysical mechanism of intumescent char formation of the composites with flame retardants, we defined the char as a separate material and added its thermal and physical properties in the code.

In FDS, the insulated boundary condition on the back surface of the sample prevents any heat loss from the back side of the material. However, in real-world cone calorimeter test with air flow around the sample, there is heat conduction between the sample and the insulating material underneath. Furthermore, there is convective loss.

Numerical Simulation of Cone Calorimeter Performance

Thermophysical properties of the materials used in the numerical model

Property	Unit	Materials				
		PP	Flax	APP	Super wool	Char
Density	kg/m ³	900	1400	1900	64	550
Emissivity	-	0.97	0.85	0.94	0.9	0.93
Specific heat capacity	kJ/kg K	2.2	1.9	1.6	1.5	1.6
Thermal conductivity	W/m K	0.18	0.3	0.4	0.12	0.1
Heat of combustion	kJ/kg	4.9×10^4	9300	-	-	-
Heat of reaction	kJ/kg	1987	1411	880	-	-
Reference temperature	°C	482	391	625	-	-
Heating rate	°C/min	20	20	20	-	-
Pyrolysis range	°C	155	145	400	-	-
Residue yield	kg/kg	0.2125	0.15	0.1	-	-
Number of reactions	-	1	1	1	-	1
Reaction order	-	3.2	1.7	3.2	-	-

Numerical Simulation of Cone Calorimeter Performance

Simulated HRR curves of the composites with an insulation layer

- The symbiotic action of treated keratinous fibre and APP was well observed.
- Improved mechanical strength helps further research into material possibilities
- This research provides a window to utilize keratinous fibre as a functional material for daily products.
- To reduce APP% in the composition.

Selected Publications in the Relevant Area

CENTRE FOR ADVANCED MATERIALS
MANUFACTURING & DESIGN

THE UNIVERSITY OF
AUCKLAND
Te Whare Wānanga o Tamaki Makaurau
NEW ZEALAND

- A Mishra, D Jung, NK Kim & D Bhattacharyya: Influence of chicken feather fibre processing technique on mechanical and fire performances of flame-retardant polypropylene composites; *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 165 (2023) 107338
- A Chanda, NK Kim & D Bhattacharyya: Effects of adhesive systems on the mechanical and fire-reaction properties of wood veneer laminates; *Comp. Sci. & Technology*, 230 (2022) 109331.
- A Chanda, N K Kim, W Wijaya, D Bhattacharyya: Fire reaction of sandwich panels with corrugated and honeycomb cores made from natural materials; *Journal of Sandwich Structures & Materials* 23 (8) (2021) 4196-4217.
- A Chanda, N K Kim, D Bhattacharyya: Manufacturing and characterisation of wood-veneer sandwich panels with flame-retardant composite cores; *Composites Communications*, 27 (2021) 100870.
- S Dutta, N K Kim, R Das, D Bhattacharyya: Evaluating Orientation Effects on the Fire Reaction Properties of Flax-Polypropylene Composites; *Polymers*, 13 (2021) 2586.
- Oisik Das, Nam Kyeun Kim, Mikael S Hedenqvist, Debes Bhattacharyya, Eva Johansson, Qiang Xu, Shima Holder: Naturally-occurring bromophenol to develop fire retardant gluten biopolymers; *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 243 (2020) 118552.
- N K Kim, F G Bruna, O Das, M S Hedenqvist, D Bhattacharyya: Fire-retardancy and mechanical performance of protein-based natural fibre-biopolymer composites; *Composites Part C: Open Access* 1, 100011 (2020).
- NK Kim, S Dutta, D Bhattacharyya: Heat and smoke production of flax fibre reinforced composites under horizontal and vertical orientations; *Composites Part B: Engineering*, Vol. 178 (2019) 1-12; Article 107467.
- S Dutta, N K Kim, R Das and D Bhattacharyya: Effects of sample orientation on the fire reaction properties of natural fibre composites; *Composites – Part B: Engineering*, Vol. 157 (2019) 195-206.
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- D Jung and D Bhattacharyya: Combined effect of silicate coating and phosphate loading on the performance improvement of a keratinous fiber-based flame retardant; *Chemical Engineering Journal* 424 (2021) 130484.
- N K Kim, A Subasinghe and D Bhattacharyya: Natural Fibres: Their Composites and Flammability Characterizations; Ch. 4 in *Multi-functionality of Polymer Composites: challenges and new solutions* (ed. K Friedrich and U Brewer) Elsevier, Waltham, MA, USA (2015) 102-143.

THANK YOU